

JCMST

NOVI SAD

2023

Supported by the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Science, Technological development and Innovation of the republic of Serbia

ABSTRACT BOOK

11 – 13 October 2023

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad

Novi Sad, Serbia

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

61(048.3)

THE PSU-UNS Joint Conference on Medical Science and Technology (2 ; 2023 ; Novi Sad)

Abstract book [Elektronski izvor] / The 2nd PSU-UNS Joint Conference on Medical Science and Technology 2023, 11-13 October 2023, Novi Sad, Serbia ; [editor-in-chief Rajko Jović]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Medicine, 2023. - 1 USB fleš memorija

Tiraž 150.

ISBN 978-86-7197-742-5

а) Медицинске науке -- Нове технологије -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 126492937

Joint Conference on
Medical Science and
Technology
NOVI SAD
2023

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ORAL PRESENTATIONS

A CHEMOMETRIC APPROACH IN DETERMINATION OF THE BIOLOGICAL SOURCE OF COMMERCIALY AVAILABLE INCENSE SAMPLES

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Introduction: Frankincense is a refined plant exudate obtained from several species of the genus *Boswellia* Roxb. Due to specific biological activity, it is used for medicinal purposes. In the process of quality control of incense, the first step is determination of the biological source. As microscopic and macroscopic and other similar pharmacognostic methods are not applicable in this case, analysis of the chemical composition can potentially reveal the biological origin of incense. The aim of this study is to discover the importance of the chemical composition of essential oils (EO) contained in incense for discovering species used to obtain incense.

Materials and methods: Isolation of EO from 15 incense samples was performed using Clevinger method. After isolation EOs were analyzed by gas chromatography coupled to mass spectroscopy. The chemical profiles of the tested samples were compared to the chemical profiles of incense available in the literature data using clustering and principal component analysis (PCA) methods.

Results: Cluster and PCA analyzes showed a clear grouping of chemical profiles available from previously published studies performed on *Boswellia papyrifera* Hochst. and four analyzed incense samples. These EOs are characterized by unique chemotaxonomic markers, among which the presence of octyl-acetate stands out as the most important. Thus, we can reasonably claim that four mentioned samples were obtained from *Boswellia papyrifera* Hochst. Literature and analytical data for other evaluated EOs show a significant degree of overlapping in term of the chemical profile, and by applying the cluster and PCA methods, they were not separated.

Conclusions: It can be concluded that the given methodology can be used to determine if incense was produced from *Boswellia papyrifera* Hochst.. In other cases, the applied methodology shows certain imperfections, due to the absence of chemotaxonomic markers.

Keywords: *Boswellia*, incense, GC-MS, essential oils